

Spectrophotometric Studies on Complex Formation of 5-Nitro-3-Sulpho-Salicylic Acid with Niobium(V)

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5-Nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic acid forms a yellow complex with niobium(V) at pH 9.9 and the reaction has been successfully studied spectrophotometrically. The results of the Job's continuous variation method and the mole ratio method indicate a composition of 1 : 2 for the complex. Stability constant of the complex has also been determined.

NIObIUM pentoxide, dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution, was found to react with 5-nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic acid. A water-soluble complex compound was formed which produced a greenish-yellow solution with maximum absorption at 405 nm. The reaction has been used for the spectrophotometric study of niobium. Application of Job's and mole ratio methods indicated the formation of 1 : 2 complex at pH 9.9. Stability constant of the complex has been determined employing Job's method.

Experimental

5-nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic acid was prepared by the method described by Meldrum¹. pH measurements were made with a pH meter using glass and calomel electrodes. All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality. Standard solutions were prepared by dissolving weighed amounts of the reagent in 30% alcohol.

Preparation of solution of niobium

Niobium pentoxide was fused with potassium bisulphate to a clear melt. The slightly cooled crucible with its contents was placed in about 200 ml of hot 2N HCl solution. The precipitated oxide was

with hot water and rinsed thoroughly with acetone. The precipitate was dried by passing air through it. Then this dried precipitate was added to 100 ml of a 0.6% sodium hydroxide solution and refluxed for about 1 hr to effect solution of the oxide. This solution was used as stock solution.

Effect of pH and time on complex formation

The solution of 5-nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic acid was added to the niobium solution, a greenish-yellow colour developed, which showed maximum absorbance at 405 nm. The system remained stable for more than 24 hr provided no evaporation took place. However, this coloured complex does not appear if the pH of the medium is below 5. The results (Fig. 1) show that pH 9.9-10.0 is most suitable for the experiment and hence was maintained in all experiments. A dilute solution of ammonia and hydrochloric acid were used for varying the pH.

Beer's Law

A series of solutions, each with a pH 9.9 and containing the same concentration ($1 \times 10^{-3}M$) of the reagent but varying concentrations of niobium(V) were prepared and their optical densities measured

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

allowed to digest for about 30 min and was then filtered. The freshly precipitated oxide was washed

at 405 nm. The results show that Beer's law is obeyed in the range 10 to 60 μg niobium (V) per ml.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

Determination of equilibrium constant

The dissociation of the complex is represented as

where α is the degree of dissociation and C is concentration of the complex. Stability constant may be written as

$$K = \frac{(1-\alpha)}{(nC\alpha)^n \alpha}$$

The value of α may be obtained from Fig. (3) by the relation

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m}$$

where E_m and E_s have usual meanings.

Thus $\alpha = .04$.

The equilibrium constant can also be calculated by the method employed by Mukherjee and Dey²⁻³. The average value of $\log K$ is 8.2949 which shows that the complex is highly stable.

Stoichiometry of the chelate

2 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ solution of niobium was taken each time and varying quantities of $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ solution of 5-nitro-3-sulpho salicylic acid added, keeping the overall volume constant. The molar ratio method (Fig. 3) showed that the stoichiometric ratio of niobium to 5-nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic acid is

1 : 2. The molar composition of the complex was further determined by Job's method of continuous variation (Fig. 4).

Effect of diverse ions

The effect of various cations and anions on the colour intensity of the complex was studied. It was found that Cu^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Mo^{6+} , Mn^{2+} , Cr^{2+} interfere and should be removed. The ions like Na^+ , K^+ , Ti^{2+} , NH_4^+ , Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , F^- and SO_4^{2-} do not interfere.

Procedure recommended for colorimetric determination

To the solution of niobium ion containing niobium (V) up to $60 \mu g$ is added a three-fold excess of 5-nitro-3-sulpho-salicylic acid. Dilute solutions of ammonium hydroxide or hydrochloric acid should be used to maintain the pH. The optical density is measured at 405 nm after shaking the mixture solution. The concentration of the unknown sample solution can be obtained by comparing absorbance of the unknown solution with the calibration curve obtained earlier.

References

1. A. N. MELDRUM and N. W. HIRWAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 7, 889.
2. A. K. MUKHERJEE and A. K. DEY, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1958, 6, 314.
3. A. K. MUKHERJEE and A. K. DEY, *Analyt. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, 18, 324.
4. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
5. D. S. PARMAR and G. C. SHIVAHARE, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 627.
6. D. S. PARMAR and G. C. SHIVAHARE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1975, 4, 296.